

Economic System- Mauryan & Gupta Empire

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Abstract:

Almost everything from the social system to the state relies on its economy. This age-old subject still applicable. Current economic crises and depressions are common. Incompetence of rulers, plagues, natural disasters, etc. harmed the economy even in ancient times. Also discussed was economic prosperity. The split of periods makes sources concerning ancient India between ancient, medieval, and contemporary Bengal sparse. Ancient Indian sources have been uncovered that are still unclear. That's why ancient India knowledge is scarce. Ancient India is studied with all its limitations. I used several books and papers for my investigation. I must carefully acquire knowledge from books and articles. After eliminating and including all data, I utilize it in my study. Additionally, coinage, property titles, copper plates, and other sources have provided economic data from that period.

Key Words- Economic, Rulers, Gupta, Mauryan, Revenue, Ancient India

Introduction-

Our everyday lives are intricately bound up with the economy. Even in ancient India, this was the case. This pattern in the economy has altered several times. Not only did political shifts occur, but the economy also saw a noticeable transformation. The economy was like a wheel; it went up and down at times. There were instances when the economic wheel was the one that shifted the balance of power. Reason being, economically powerful monarchs intended to invade adjacent nations in order to gain power for themselves. Thus, the governing elite sought to ensure the state's economic affairs ran smoothly. The level of economic activity during a

given era determined whether of ancient India's policymakers—the Maurya, the Gupta, or someone else entirely—was in charge. Whether the rulers were competent or not was also linked to this. The average Indian also played a crucial part in ancient India's thriving economy. The ordinary people of ancient India were more engaged in agriculture since it was the mainstay of the economy. Furthermore, the economic system was closely related to ancient India's foreign policy. These monetary features of ancient India will be the focus of the current investigation. Through this we want to find out the clear path of the economic condition of the period. That being said,

Fig: Maurya Empire.

This study primarily focuses on the interplay and significance of the following themes: the role of rulers, the ordinary people, power, and the economy.

Maurya Empire

The essential information on the Maurya dynasty may be gleaned from all these sources. When Kautilya was offended in 322 BC, Chandragupta Maurya formed the Mauryan Empire, according to these accounts. Author of the "Arthashastra" Chandragupta Maurya convened an army and deposed the Nanda Empire with the assistance of Kautilya, whose alternate name is Chanakya. Ending in the fourth century BC, with the arrival of the Mauryas, India's history was both illuminated and shrouded in mystery. The first member of the Maurya family to become an emperor was Chandragupta. No one can agree on when exactly Chandragupta Maurya became king. Reason being, accounts of it vary among sources. No first-hand narrative of the Nanda dynasty's downfall has been preserved by Chandragupta Maurya. This requires us to draw from a variety of resources.

When researching the Maurya Empire, you may choose between two main sorts of sources. There is an archeological one and a literary one. Literature from the Maurya Empire comes from a wide variety of sources, including both local and foreign writers. Included among the indigenous sources are the works of Kautilya (Arthashastra), Vishakhadatta (Mudraraksasa), Banvatta (Harshacharita, biography of Harshabardhana), Kalahana (Rajtarangini), Jain (Parvana) and Buddhist (Traditions) texts, among many more. Greek Buddhist megawritten sources, Pliny's "Natural History" (AD 72), Pali Buddhist scriptures from Sri Lanka, and the narratives of three Chinese adventurers—FaHien, Hiuen Tsang, and I-Tsing—are all part of the canon. The inscriptions on the edicts of Ashoka are the epigraphic sources that are accessible today. Based on the rock's surface, there are three distinct types of Ashokan inscriptions. Rock, pillar, and cave edicts are what they're called. A rock edict might be either a big or a minor edict. Girnar, Kharoshti-scripted Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Mansehra, Yerragudi, DhauliJaugada, Sopara, Kalsi, Sannati, and Kandahar are some of the most important rock edicts in the country. Kandahar bilingual inscriptions, Bhabru rock edicts, etc. are all examples of Minoan rule. Ashokan edicts and inscriptions, as well as artifacts like golden, silver, and copper coins, are among the archaeological sources.

Chandragupta Maurya was persuaded by King Dhana Nanda to capture the realm of the Nanda. In his vow of vengeance, Kautilya promised to wipe out the Nanda Empire. He planned to invade the Nanda Empire after training an army under

Chandragupta Maurya's leadership. Kautilya advised Chandragupta Maurya and his soldiers to seize the kingdom of Magadha. King Dhana Nanda's corrupt and tyrannical leadership had the people of Magadha fuming at the time. In preparation for his conquest of Dhana Nanda's empire, Chandragupta Maurya mustered an army. He gave the order to go to war, and the Magadha army was marched out of the city to meet the Mauryan army at a distant battleground. Civil conflict was sown by Chandragupta Maurya in the Dhana Nanda empire, and the ordinary people's attitude was echoed by Kautilya. Nanda eventually abdicated, ceded control, and disappeared into exile, leaving no trace behind. In 322 BC, at the age of 21, Chandragupta Maurya was lawfully seated as the new king of Magadha, and Kautilya became the elder statesman. Magadha was the seat of authority for Chandragupta Maurya, who also made Pataliputra (modern-day Patna) his capital. During Ashoka's reign, the empire reached its height, spanning a territory of almost 5 million square kilometers—the biggest on the Indian subcontinent. The assistance of Kautilya allowed Chandragupta Maurya to swiftly increase his authority. The Maurya Empire was massive by international standards during that era. The northern boundary of the empire was the Himalayas, while the western boundaries were Assam, Baluchistan, and the Hindu Kush Mountains in modern-day Afghanistan. Although the southern and central portions of India were expanded by the empire under Bindusara and Chandragupta Maurya, a tiny section of the tribal and woodland districts around Kalinga remained untouched until Ashoka conquered them. After Ashoka's reign ended, the empire declined for over half a millennium. In 185 BCE, the Shunga dynasty was established in Magadha, dissolving the Maurya dynasty.

The Mauryan Economic System:

As a result of a streamlined system of finance, administration, and adequate security put in place by Chandragupta Maurya and his successors, economic activities including as agriculture, trade, and internal and external commerce thrived and spread across South Asia. During that period, the Maurya Empire had a highly developed economy.

Agriculture:

The majority of the Maurya population resided in rural areas and engaged in agriculture. Land development was a priority for the Maurya monarchs as agriculture was a major source of revenue throughout their reign. Along with cash aid, land grants were also distributed to low-income farmers so they could cultivate their crops. In order to make way for new agricultural regions, the state cleared fallen trees and cleared the forest. Although legislation did exist to preserve certain woods, not all forests were so fortunate. A direct line to the monarch was established by the farmer. Several

crops were farmed throughout the Mauryan era. These included rice, coarse grains, sesame, pepper, saffron, pulses, wheat, bamboo, paddy, mustard, linseed, vegetables, sugarcane, and a variety of fruits.

Ownership of the land:

Dayodorous brought up the fact that the land belonged to the monarch. No one could ever be a property owner, in his view. Regarding property rights to land, Megasthenes made similar remarks. Regarding the ownership of the land by the royal family, there are several competing theories that have taken root. Some historians argue that while the monarch was a tax collector and guardian of the land, he did not really possess it. What is noteworthy, however, is what "Manu-Shamhita" says on the king who owned the property. The "Manu-Shamhit" states that the monarch is supreme over all creation. You can't have it both ways with these two tenets. The commonly held belief today is that while the monarch did not really possess the property outright, he did have some privileges associated with it. It was noted in "Arthashastra" that the monarch had certain land holdings that were managed by the government for cultivation. There was also reference to further taxpayer-owned property.

Land system:

Dr. Basu said that the system in the nation was different. There were three distinct soil kinds. The peasants, the state, or a combination of the three could have possessed the land at one point. Additionally, he said that renters' rights to land are progressively expanding. The two concepts of shared ownership and prior ownership of property were distinct. "Arthashastra" even hinted at peasant rights. Peasants who showed little interest in farming may potentially have their land confiscated by the monarch. The regulation, however, was revised more recently. The land was transferred to another party for development if deemed required. So, land ownership would remain the same. According to Dr. Basu, the country's monarch and farmer had equal rights. There was a noticeable shift toward individual ownership rather than collective ownership.

Land Revenue system:

The findings of Dr. Ghoshala's "Indian Revenue System" Under the Maurya Empire, land sales were the backbone of India's economy. Shita, Vag, Bali, and Kara were the four types of land taxes imposed by the Maurya kingdom. The Shita tax was associated with the royal farm's produce. The royal irrigation system was accessible to farmers who paid a water levy. The farmer was liable for a fifth of the harvest if he drew the water by hand, a fourth if he relied on an animal, and a third if he used equipment. A quarter of the harvest was due as taxation if the farmer used water from

bodies of water like rivers or lakes. All harvests would be sent to the royal treasury if they were farmed using state-owned machinery by inmates, slaves, or free laborers overseen by a public official. Distributing oxen to cultivate unproductive land would result in half of the harvest going to that person, while manual laborers would get a quarter or a fifth. The remainder of the crop was paid into the royal coffers. Two distinct territorial divisions existed within the Maurya Empire. Only certain types of land were subject to the state tax. Taxes were required on one-sixth of the harvest from certain fields. According to D.D. Koshamvi, the second-rate nation was known as ShitaJamin. It was the king's job to oversee farming and settlement in this land. During the Mauryan era, ShitaJamin comprises the majority of the landmass. It was known as the Shita tax, and it applied to all of these nations. Special authorization was required for the transfer of land at that time. Someone else would inherit land from an agrarian who died. If the settlement was new or if it occurred during a disaster, the shift tax was waived. At its most basic, the Shita tax rate was 20% of harvest.

•Vag—Vag was the name of the second tax. The Vag tax was the king's portion of the land's harvest that was subject to this tax. Two such forms of taxation were the Bali and Kara levies. Many historians believe that these taxes were partial. Particular lands and employment types were the primary targets of these two levies.

Land income and commercial activity were the backbone of the Maurya Empire's finances. Land revenue rose as a result of the agricultural economy's progressive development and the upgrading of the administrative infrastructure for tax collection. According to Kautilya, the state should take care of the shudra cultivator settlements and provide for the removal of wastelands. There was some disagreement on the specifics of the land income. In addition, the cultivation of royal lands is mentioned, which played a significant role in the economy. One form of tax was based on the total area of land, while the other kind was based on the harvest from that land. The states only kept the irrigation system in working order for short stints and in some locations. Landowners and cultivators also have private control over the irrigation infrastructure. Both domestic and international commerce were also subject to revenue policies. In order to facilitate quick contact with the local authorities, highways were constructed during that period. These roads later became major thoroughfares for commerce and exchange. The major thoroughfares of commerce were laced with latrines. Consequently, commercial interests were enhanced. Royal treasury was bolstered via the imposition of duties on imports and exports.

Greek authors like Megasthenes made significant remarks on the land and tax system throughout the Mauryan era. In his three remarks on the matter, Megasthenes -

1. There were more farmers, making them the second most numerous nation in India. Without paying any land tax, they offered the king 25% of their harvest.
2. The monarch owned all the land. Assuming he receives 25% of the harvest, the farmer tends to the land.
3. Peasants contributed to the king and autonomous towns via their agricultural labor.

A large sum of money was required to meet the king's fundamental and everyday requirements. A large number of paid workers were there alongside the military. Revenue was to be used mostly for the purchase of state-owned property. There were less stable and assured sources of governmental revenue. Consequently, the quantity of state land was expanded via a variety of means. His property would have been seized by the state in the absence of a valid will. All the expansive terrain was turned into arable land, and the uncultivated areas were leveled for the benefit of renters. Those who lived on uncultivated land were paid rent rather than given legal title. Several land revenue price proposals were made by Megasthenes, Ariyan, Diadorous, and Strabo. The people who lived there "tended the land and paid taxes to the king or independent cities," as stated by Ariyan. The whole territory of India was owned by the monarch, and no one could own land there; so, everybody paid a land tax to the king, as stated by Diodorus. A quarter of the harvest went into the royal treasury, on top of taxes. The state was required to receive "three-quarters" of the crop income as land revenue, according to Strabo, while farmers were paid a quarter as wages. I don't know whether the variation in the farmer's soil cultivation conditions or anything else caused the production rate to be different. The rate of return may have been lower in cases where the monarch just granted the farmer land, and greater in cases where he also supplied the ploughs, oxen, fertilizer, etc., that were necessary for farming. The disparity in wealth is noted in the "Arthashastra" as well. The community served as a unit of economic production in those days. The two taxes, Vag and Bali, connected every village to the central authority. Anyone who created a new pond or repaired an old one would be free of the fee, they said. Farmers were shielded from many forms of loss by the state.

Trade and commerce:

The growth of commerce in India was facilitated by the political cohesion and internal stability of the Mauryan Empire. The Mauryan empire's network of foreign merchants flourished during Ashoka's rule. As a trading post and gateway

to the outside world, the Khabar Pass rose to strategic prominence. Western Asian Greek and Hellenic kingdoms began trade with one another. Additionally, the Malay Peninsula became a trading post for Southeast Asian countries. As a result, the government became the country's top trader and had no choice but to regulate all commerce to safeguard its interests. The state's right to set prices served as the foundation for trade regulation. Trade and commerce were subject to various levies that were imposed in various ways. Despite the government's unfriendly stance against merchants, commerce did contribute to the treasury. Merchants were referred to as "Achaurashchar" in "Arthashastra"—not by name, but in a derogatory sense, like a robber. Foreign nations enjoyed cordial connections with the Mauryas. The Mauryans fostered friendly ties with several western nations, including Syria, Egypt, and others, in order to facilitate commerce. During that period, commerce and manufacturing were booming.

The towns of the Mauryan dynasty were home to many merchants from other countries. Some provisions could not have been avoided when establishing the pricing control system. It was forbidden to sell any commodities in their field or factory of origin. The next step was to bring them to the approved marketplaces, or pannya-sala, where the vendor may have their wares assessed for quality, quantity, and price. Obtaining a license to sell was mandatory for all merchants. A passport was also required of the foreign dealer. Items were brought in and out of the country. Some items were so popular in the Mauryan empire that the rulers would bring them in from outside. Rugs, carpets, figs, jewels, coins, wines, and exquisite silverware are all examples. They export some value products just as much as they import some vital ones from elsewhere. The exported muslins and jamdani fabrics were in great demand. A distinct department was established to oversee trade and commerce, which quickly became very lucrative for the empire. This agency was responsible for introducing a transparent system. All products were officially stamped and measured using standard weights and measurements. When the Mauryas started engaging in marine commerce later in their reign, they began building ships and leasing them out to traders. While the Maurya dynasty did not have a central bank, they did have a mechanism for exchanging money. Goods imported and exported were subject to taxes. Goods were the only things that could be taxed. Throughout, export and import tariffs were used to tax trade. How he went about his business was crucial. Roads and rivers both played important roles in the Maurya Empire's commercial network.

Other Taxes:

A large portion of the Mauryan government's coffers were filled by land taxes

(Shita, Vag, Bali and Kara). There was monetary transactions, even if land taxes were the primary (though not exclusive) source of income. Neither were artists and craftspeople immune from paying taxes. It is also important to note the following taxes:

A levy known as the Shenavaktam was levied in order to fund the army.

The monetary present given at the birth of a prince was known as the Utshanga tax. Also contributing to the state coffers were brothels, casinos, nightclubs, and slaughterhouses. The money was loaned by the state. Not only would this money be due, but the interest would also bring in a tidy sum for the government. A tax was imposed on all municipal residents who owned their own house. Revenue from irrigation, ferry crossings, etc., was substantial. The treasury also received fines that were levied during judicial procedures. The king would inherit any remaining property. It was official state policy to own any loot discovered inside the state. In times of crisis, additional levies were imposed. Lands, woods, and mines owned by the royal family were regarded as state property. The wealth generated by these mines allowed the monarch to amass forces. The production of salt was reserved for the state. A modest rate of tax might be applied to imported salt. Including the alloy in the money also brought in money for the government. Earnings from unemployed labor were also taken into account.

Taxes were a major hardship for those who were not Brahmin under the Maurya Empire. War, evangelism, and public welfare all relied heavily on tax revenue. Consequently, the tax load was quite heavy. Tax collectors repress renters when it comes to collecting taxes. Uprisings broke out in several areas of the Maurya Empire as a result of the tax system.

Revenue Administration:

The role of tax administration during the Mauryan era was described by Dr. Ghoshal. According to him, the "Arthashastra" makes it unclear what role the minister has in handling tax administration. However, the "Manu-Shamhita" said that the monarch was to choose an official to handle matters pertaining to the treasury. Two prominent officials, "Shamarhata" and "Shanniddhayta," were described in the "Arthashastra." The major authority over the management of economic issues belonged to them. They were on an equal footing. An annual compensation of 24,000 silver coins was theirs. Financial and other obligations fell on both of them. Šamarhat also had responsibilities pertaining to criminal and public justice. It was part of his job as a police officer to keep tabs on merchants and monks via the use of spies. He was responsible for handling the state's revenue and expenditures so that he could meet his financial responsibilities. Ports,

mines, irrigation systems, forests, commercial routes, etc. were all within his purview. He was supposed to increase income while decreasing expenses. He had to boost revenue significantly throughout the crisis. The government buildings were built and maintained by Shanniddhayta. He oversaw the national treasury. The quantity of money must have seemed weird to him. At the lowest levels, Šamarhata and Shanniddhayta served as superintendents and were chosen after passing a specific test.

Financial management was also carried out by three additional types of staff. What they were It was Gopp's responsibility to keep track of the money for the five or ten communities they were in charge of Sthanik—A fifth of the state was under their control. As a result, they had to cover more ground in their recordings. It is well-documented that Pradeshtas were used for tax collection within their sphere of influence.

Wholesale pricing were determined by the trade commander. The profit margin, he let determine the sale price. People faced harsh consequences for engaging in smuggling and counterfeiting products. The government outlawed worker strikes in an effort to increase pay. It was the state's duty to safeguard its citizens, clients, and consumers against unsanctioned pricing and deceitful transactions. Along with training merchants to recognize and avoid fraudulent product claims, the state also sent a slew of spies and market inspectors to patrol trade channels. At all times, the shipment's whereabouts were tracked. The government officer in charge of the area they were going through was supposed to replace anything lost during passage. Responsibility was vested in a village's headman, who was known as Grama-Svami or Grama-mukhya. Dacoit gangs from other countries, warring Mlechchha tribes (such as the Kirats), and woodland dwellers on the prowl for loot all need vigilant trade protection in bygone days. Hunters and dog breeders, however, stood watch over every community.

The rise and fall of the Maurya Empire were unprecedented events in ancient Indian history. There were no competent successors to Emperor Ashoka, and the empire fell into ruin. In his account of the collapse of the Mauryan Empire, Dr. Niharranjan Roy brings up the topic of popular uprising. He claims the Maurya rulers' excessive taxation was the root cause of the uprising. A fourth of the crop was taxed, which was a very low amount compared to Megasthenes. Dr. Koshamvi claims that the post-Ashoka era was a difficult one for the Mauryan economy. Since prostitutes were also subject to taxes during that era. In addition, there was a dramatic spike in the forgery of the era's coinage. However, Dr. Romeela Thapar was opposed to it. He claims that it was during the

Mauryan era that he first understood the significance of tax. Consequently, taxing anything that might be considered taxable was the norm throughout that period. It was the usual for these taxes. Another option for hiding money is to increase currency counterfeiting.

Gupta Empire

The collapse of the Mauryan empire severely fractured Indian history. Reason being, after the Mauryans, no monarch dared to emulate their actions. In addition, the majority of India was governed by foreign powers for an extended period after the Mauryas. The Kushana dynasty brought India back together for a while, but after they fell, it was never the same. The Gujrat and Malavar kingdoms were part of the short-lived Shaka dynasty. A second major empire, this one centered on Magadha and ruled by the Guptas, emerged roughly 500 years after the Maurya Empire collapsed. The Indian subcontinent was once again united, peaceful, and prosperous during the Gupta dynasty. Gupta rule lasted longer than Maurya rule, despite the fact that the Gupta dynasty was shorter. According to some historians, the Gupta dynasty was India's most prosperous era. Chandragupta I, Samudragupta, and

Chandragupta II were the most influential and famous members of the Gupta dynasty, which was established by King Sri Gupta. As the third century AD drew to a close, three major Indian empires rose to prominence. In western India, the Midlands saw the Varsib Nagas, in the Deccan, the Bakatakas, and in eastern India, the Guptas. The precise tribe to which the Guptas belonged is unknown. It is also difficult to pinpoint the precise location of the original adobe. Henrik Prayag and the Guptas were feudal lords under the Varsib Nags of the Western Midlands, according to historians. Numerous people have rediscovered Magadha as their ancestral dwelling place, using Vayu, Vishnu, and BhagabataPurana as justification. Once at a time, AS. Altekar had this opinion. Yet, his confidence in the subject waned as time went on. Since Bihar did not provide any coins minted by Chandragupta I, the first king of the Gupta dynasty. Additional information was provided by Dr. D.C. Ganguli later on. He determined that the Guptas' abode was Murshidabad in Bangla. Dr. Goyal states that the Guptas resided in Allahbad and the Yukta Pradesh region of eastern India.

Fig: Gupta Empire.

Geographical area. Therefore, he focused on Gupta texts and coinage, particularly the location of the Allahbad Prashasti. This area of Uttar Pradesh has yielded fourteen hoards of Gupta gold coins, compared to only two hoards in Bihar and Bengal. Eastern Uttar Pradesh was the site of six inscriptions, Magadha of two, and Bengal of five, all dating back to the first 150 years of the Gupta rule. According to the Harishena Prashasti, Samudra gupta had a particular fondness for the Allahbad region. That the first Gupta dynasty ruled over the heart of the country in eastern Uttar Pradesh is so readily apparent.

There are primarily three types of artifacts from the Gupta era: inscriptions, coinage, and literature. The finest Gupta-era inscription was that of Samudragupta, which was found on a pillar. His inscriptions at Nalanda, Gaya, and Aaron are equally remarkable. Important information is also included in the Chandragupta II pillar inscriptions at Mathura. The largest number of inscriptions was fourteen, which Kumaragupta I had. The Third Udaipur Cave Inscription, Mandasor Inscription, and Damodarpur Inscription are three of the most notable. Important information is provided by Skandhagupta's Junnagarh, Supiya, and Vitari inscriptions. Learn important details from the Budhgupta inscriptions found at Saranath, Paharpur, Rajghat, and Damodarpur on copper plates. During the Gupta era, coins made of gold, silver, and copper were in circulation. It seems that the gold coins from that time were just knockoffs of the Kushangold coins. Nevertheless, this does not meet all standards. Gold coin counterfeiting rose throughout the Gupta era, and the quantity of gold in circulation fell. That fluctuations in the price of gold portend a catastrophic economic collapse. The history of the Gupta dynasty might be better understood with the aid of these many gold coins that have been discovered around India. By analyzing these coins, we may piece together the Gupta dynasty's past.

Literature, along with inscriptions and coinage, contributes to the chronicle of that era's history. The Purana is a reliable historical text among them. Sources such as "Aryamanjusrimulkalpa," Bajjika's play "Kaumudini Mahotshaba," Vishakhadutta's drama "Devi Chadraguptam," and Kamandaka's "Nitisara" provided crucial details on the Gupta kingdom. You may piece together the Gupta dynasty's history using bits and pieces from these three sources. The Gupta economic system: The Gupta era was characterized by widespread cultural advancement due to the period's stable and prosperous economy. While agriculture played a crucial part in the Gupta Empire, commerce and manufacturing also saw substantial growth. Agriculture played a significant

role in the Gupta Empire, just as it did in the Mauryan Empire. The Gupta period saw economic growth and prosperity as a result of increased commerce and agricultural output.

Agriculture:

One of the Gupta Empire's pillars was agriculture. As a result of their emphasis on agriculture, the Gupta economy thrived. The Gupta rulers used scientific ways to enhance agricultural productivity, and the system of agriculture was already advanced at this time.

Land ownership:

When asked about land ownership during the Gupta era, historians have offered varying opinions. According to Dr. Basák, the state did not possess the property back then. Here, he presented not one but two reasons. First, not even the state could transfer property to someone without the general public's agreement; this included Mahamatra and another businessman, who were both district representatives of the people. The second point he presented was that the state treasury would legitimately get one-sixth of the selling revenues, as stated in a gift document discovered in Faridpur. The remaining funds' intended use remained unclear. Gram-Shava would end up with one fifth of the remaining six. Basak put out two reasons, which Dr. Ghoshal sought to disprove. According to Ghoshal, Dr. Basaka's view was not supported by enough evidence. The official figures of the Gupta period, he said, were not included in the inscriptions concerning this matter. There is some mention of lesser workers, but no proof that their permission was needed to sell the property. A misunderstanding of the term "Dharmasaravaga" is the foundation of Basak's second argument, in his view. The true sense of this term is a portion of religious excellence. At that time, the property could only be purchased by those who could provide written notice to the buyer that the land would be transferred for religious reasons only. Therefore, everyone thought the monarch would give in to the buyer's demands and take a cut of the profits. Nonetheless, the common belief is that peasants owned property for a considerable portion of the Gupta era.

A North Bengali inscription stands out as a clear outlier. It seems that the local community and the state had shared ownership of the property. The authority to convey property was shared between the monarch and the local councils. At this time, there is no easy way to decide on a plan for the whole state's geography. Even though the king's barns were stocked with grain to stave off starvation, the common belief was that he had no business having so much of it. The state's impoverished population received food distributions during the famine. The "AGRAHAARA" grants that the monarch might make may be revoked after he passed away. During

the Gupta dynasty, the monarch enjoyed absolute power. While the Guptas were in power, rice, wheat, sugarcane, bamboo, and other crops were staples in their diet. The agricultural irrigation system was given particular care by the Gupta rulers. The territory was bestowed to the Buddhist Church by the Gupta emperors. The church acted as a banking and helped anybody in need of financial assistance. Lending money at this time was more affordable than it had been during the Maurya Empire. An interest rate was not predetermined since no policy was issued by the government. Both sides would have to agree for the interest rate to be greater than the current one. Easy and reasonably priced access to capital was a beneficial aspect that contributed to the Gupta Empire's economic growth.

There are several ways to categorize the terrain that existed during the Gupta era:

- Kshetra: Land suitable for farming.
- Khala means desolate terrain.
- Aprahita: root system of a forest or jungle.
- Vacanti means livable land.
- Saratoga means pasture.

Irrigation system:

One of the primary responsibilities of the Gupta dynasty rulers was to ensure the general improvement of agriculture since it was a major source of revenue at that time. Therefore, the agrarian lands' irrigation system was well-maintained by the kings using various means. Here were the procedures:

- **Tank:** A widely used method of watering crops during the Gupta era. After suffering extensive damage during the Mahakshatraps, the Sudersana tank in Saurashtra underwent full restoration. It was restored by Skandhagupta.
- **Wells:** This was still another way water might be supplied. Here, canals were dug and water was piped from wells to the crops.

This method, known as the Chain of Pot Method, was in use long before the Gupta era. The system used a series of interconnected pots held together by a chain; the chain extended to the water level of the hull, and the pots were continuously filled and emptied as the operator turned the chain and the pots. Araghatta and Gati were other names for this technique.

Another recognized form of reservoir, ponds were used to collect rainfall in ancient India. One possible solution in southern India is tank irrigation. It was the responsibility of the Gupta Empire's government to ensure that its growers had access to the several forms of irrigation that were commonplace there.

- Kshetra: cultivable land.
- Khila: barren land.
- Aprahita: jungle or forest floor.
- Vasti: habitable land.

- Gapata Sarah: pasture.

Trade and Commerce:

During the Gupta era, industrialization was in full swing. Important to the Gupta Empire's economy was the textile sector. There were a lot of things made and sent out by this sector of the economy. Muslin, flax, silk, wheat, spices, salt, bullion, calico, wool, cotton, and so on were among the most important commodities. Other Gupta Empire industries included carving and molding stone, as well as working with ivory. Additionally, jewelry made of valuable metals including pearls, copper, iron, bronze, and silver was highly sought for. However, ceramics was the Gupta period's most significant industry. Numerous gold coins were circulated by the Gupta emperors. Dinars were the name given to these golden coins. Among ancient Indian empires, the Guptas' gold coins have been the most abundantly discovered. Silver coins were also minted by the Gupta kings. Silver coins were first created during the Gupta period by Emperor Chandragupta I. Coins made of lead and rare copper were also circulated throughout the Gupta period. European nations, as well as China and Ceylon, were trading partners of the Gupta Empire. Chinese silk and East African ivory were imported by the Guptas. The Gupta Empire's trade hub shifted to Southeast Asia at this time. The empire's commercial operations were very streamlined and effective. The Roman Empire began to ease its trade restrictions about the year 550 AD.

Under the Gupta dynasty, the leather industry also thrived. Artworks from the modern era often included footwear made of leather, such as boots and shoes. The jewelry art form has progressed to a more refined level. The "Brihat-Samhita" makes reference to about 22 different types of gems. There were a lot of various functions for jewelry back then. The profusion of brass, gold, and silver was also noted by Hiwen-Tsang. Ancient coinage, including seals and coins made of gold, silver, and copper, attests to the period's sophisticated metalworking. The Gupta dynasty was also notable for its advanced shipbuilding industry, which aided in communication and commerce. Both colonization and commerce benefited from this. The mining and metallurgical sectors stood out among the many that thrived under the Gupta era. For the most part, guilds remained the backbone of the manufacturing and trading industries. Weavers and stone cutters were among the many manual laborers who belonged to guilds alongside bankers and merchants. These guilds had enough independence to run their own businesses and take part in the people's economic life. For banking, member dispute settlement, and the issuance of hundis and coins, they relied on their own property and trusts. These guilds were vital to the production of

products and to the improvement of the empire's economic standing. All merchants were required to follow the rules set down by their respective guilds.

Animals were the primary means of transportation for commodities throughout that era. Travel by road and water were the main means of trade. Along with Gaya, Pataliputra, Vaishali, Banaras, Kausambi, Mathura, Peshawar, and Prayag, the Gupta era saw the establishment of many more significant cities. Public highways linked these cities, and the state ensured the safety of its citizens and merchants by providing all necessary amenities. Trade between eastern and western nations was common for the Guptas. Maritime trade with the Byzantine Empire, Sri Lanka, Persia, Africa, Arabia, and other regions was common practice for the Gupta dynasty. During the Gupta period, many seaports played a significant role:

- Tamralipti
- Arikamedu
- Muziris
- Barbaricum
- Kaveripattanam
- Pratihasthana
- Brighukachchha
- Sopara

All corners of the Gupta Empire's interior roads led to these ports.

Revenue system:

The Gupta era placed a premium on taxation and the revenue system. There is less information on the Gupta period's taxation system in the inscriptions from that era. During the Gupta era, these were the levies that were widely accepted:

- Treasury contributions for land: a quarter or half of the harvest went into this pot. Just what it sounds like: a tax on land.
- Vog Kara or Chungi Kara: workers of the town and village were required to pay this tax as part of their compensation. Products were subject to this levy.
- Bhootpratya, also known as the consumption tax, was imposed on all produced commodities inside the empire. Ports, ferries, and protected towns were also subject to taxes. The state was the rightful owner of the degraded land, woods, and salt mines. Rentals or sales of items derived from them were the main sources of income. Local institutions were entrusted with the management of the state-owned fallow land.

That "only those who cultivated state land had to pay a portion of the grain" is what Fa-Hien writes. His comment muddled the thoughts of historians. It is widely believed that the majority of the funds were obtained via the leasing of state-owned property. Nonetheless, there is a little flaw in this theory. The state's revenue from alcoholic beverages should be disregarded if Fa-Hien's

evidence is believed. The selling of alcoholic beverages was envisioned in "Arthashastra" as a way for the state to generate income. Even throughout the Gupta era, consuming alcohol was not outright forbidden, according to documents from both the pre- and post-Gupta periods. In the early 5th century, the Middle Kingdom was supposedly an affluent and joyful place to live, according to Fa-Hien. He went on to say that India had a comparable picture of peace and development. Affluence and the comforts of city life were likewise preserved by the populace.

Land revenue was the state's primary source of income throughout the Gupta dynasty. 'Uparikara' (octroi), a kind of taxation imposed on textiles, oils, and other products, was one type of production that was declared as royal income. Traders were robbed of their 'Sulka' whenever they transferred any form of product from one city to another. A merchant was fined up to eight times the initial "Sulk" if he failed to provide the "Sulk" or canceled the cargo.

Revenue administration:

A number of individuals were designated to carry out this function:

- Pustapala (keeper of records): Prior to documenting any transaction, Pustapala interviewed the interviewee and thereafter recorded various details about the transaction.

In addition to reclaiming her royal responsibilities, Gopasramini entered other problems with accounting opponents. Additionally, he fined people for losses caused by carelessness or fraud and cheekily embezzled money.

Conclusion

Income from land was the backbone of the economy throughout the Mauryan and Gupta dynasties. The bulk of the empire's population was rural, agricultural laborers in both eras. They were the economic engine that never stopped spinning. Though it paled in comparison to land income, the royal treasury was nonetheless benefited by trade and commerce. To manage their enormous empires, kings and queens of the Maurya and Gupta periods required legions of trained warriors. That massive army required a substantial budget, to reiterate. Furthermore, leaders should consistently take precautions to avoid hostility from outside forces and keep positive ties with the global community.

In both periods, a large amount of money was required for agricultural pursuits, trade and commerce, and the establishment of cordial connections with foreign nations. So, the kings and queens did a lot to foster trade and commerce and grow the agricultural sector. This is how the kings and queens enriched themselves monetarily. Even if no empire could remain in power indefinitely, those in charge certainly weren't naive in their attempts to maintain economic stability. The leaders began their efforts to ensure the revenue system's general

success with the selection of competent treasurers. This allowed the monarchs to keep their governments well-funded and running smoothly. The rulers of both times used much the same strategy to keep their economies booming. During both times, the watering system and income collection functioned without a hitch.

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